

Fixed Intelligence Mindsets Predict System Legitimization in Educational Contexts

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Abstract

Growth and fixed mindsets (i.e., beliefs about whether or not people's abilities can be developed) shape how people interpret and respond to events in their social worlds. The present work examines how these mindsets relate to individuals' likelihood of legitimizing racial and socioeconomic inequities in education. Meta-analyses of 20 original studies including K-12 teachers and staff members ($k = 8$; $N \approx 2,001$), college students ($k = 7$; $N \approx 2,725$), and American adults ($k = 5$; $N \approx 1,792$) demonstrated that the belief that intelligence is an unchangeable characteristic (i.e., *fixed mindset*) consistently predicted greater likelihood of legitimizing educational inequalities via five different measures of legitimization. These results suggest that fixed mindsets about intelligence are likely to undermine policy-driven efforts to change inequitable educational systems, and that one pathway toward educational equity involves attending to prevailing beliefs about the possibilities of growing one's intelligence.

Keywords: fixed mindset, system legitimization, education, inequality

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1. Introduction

National educational data reveal a dispiriting truth: across numerous indicators, the U.S. education system consistently produces lower-quality educational outcomes (e.g., academic performance, graduation rates) for students from disadvantaged racial (i.e., Black, Latino/a, Native American) and socioeconomic (i.e., lower-income) backgrounds relative to their peers from White, Asian, and higher-income families (Hanuschek et al., 2023; Reardon et al., 2019). Although these disparities have been the topic of conversation for decades, we have yet to see change in many of the educational policies that give rise to their existence. For example, the use of property taxes to fund local schools leads students from lower-income neighborhoods--many of whom are racial/ethnic minorities (Morgan, 2022)--to receive fewer and lower quality educational resources and opportunities compared to students in higher-income neighborhoods (Turner et al., 2016). Given this disparity, it is not surprising that students from lower-income neighborhoods often have poorer academic outcomes than their wealthier peers (Nieuwenhuis et al., 2021; Wodtke et al., 2016). After nearly 50 years of debate over the inequity of using property taxes to fund schools, however, few states have made meaningful changes, leaving in place policies that are known to produce inequitable outcomes (Kenyon et al., 2022).

The causes of educational policy stagnation are inarguably multifaceted and rooted in a variety of cultural, political, and economic systems. Driving all of these systems, however, are individuals, whose beliefs are both shaped by and, in turn, shapers of their social worlds and the policies and practices that guide these worlds (Markus & Hamdani, 2019). Educational

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

policies -- or any policies -- are unlikely to change if individuals do not believe that the outcomes that arise from these policies need to be--or even can be--changed. In this paper, we explore how powerful and widespread beliefs about the nature of intelligence relate to individuals' preferences for policies that maintain versus alleviate educational inequities. Specifically, we focus on *fixed intelligence beliefs*, which construe intelligence as an inherent and unchangeable characteristic of individuals (Dweck, 1999; Dweck et al., 1995, 1993). Through a meta-analysis of 20 original studies that include college students, K-12 educators, and American adults, we explore how individuals' endorsement of fixed intelligence beliefs relates to their likelihood of justifying inequitable educational systems and rejecting policies that aim to make these systems more equitable.

1.1 Intelligence Mindsets as Frameworks for Meaning-Making

As people make sense of the world around them, they draw on lay theories (also referred to as *mindsets*) about the extent to which people's attributes are fixed versus malleable (Dweck et al., 1995; Dweck et al., 1993; Dweck & Yeager, 2019). People who endorse *fixed mindsets* believe that individuals' characteristics are unchangeable realities, while people who endorse *growth mindsets* believe that those same characteristics can be developed (Dweck, 1999; Dweck et al., 1995, 1993). For example, people who endorse *fixed intelligence mindsets* view intelligence as innate and unchangeable. They believe that people are born with a certain amount of intelligence that is outside of their control, and some people are simply more intelligent than others. When such individuals experience failure, their mindsets often lead them to interpret failure as an indication that they lack intellectual ability and that there is little they can do to change their outcomes (Blackwell et al., 2007; Cury et al., 2008; Dweck et

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

al., 1995; Nussbaum & Dweck, 2008; Robins & Pals, 2002). People who endorse *growth intelligence mindsets*, however, view intelligence as something that can be changed through hard work, good strategies, and effective support. These individuals are more likely to interpret failure as surmountable and therefore persist in the face of setbacks (e.g., Aditomo, 2015; Blackwell et al., 2007; Hong et al., 1999).

Intelligence mindsets shape students' interpretation of their own academic experiences, but they also shape how teachers evaluate and respond to students (e.g., Canning et al., 2019; Paunesku et al., 2015; Rattan et al., 2012; Yeager & Dweck, 2012; Yeager et al., 2019). Teachers who endorse fixed intelligence mindsets are more likely to believe that struggling students are simply destined to struggle, whereas those who endorse growth intelligence mindsets believe that these students can improve if they use effective strategies and receive the necessary support (see Canning et al., 2019). These differing interpretations of student potential shape how teachers support struggling students. Teachers who endorse fixed intelligence mindsets may be more likely to accept resignation and provide comfort to struggling students, as opposed to encouraging students to persist in an effort to improve their performance (Rattan et al., 2012). In essence, teachers' endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predisposes them to take actions (or to *not* take actions) that reinforce existing patterns in student performance.

1.2 Making Meaning of Educational Inequality

Intelligence mindsets have often been studied in the context of education, where their implications for individuals' motivation, engagement, and performance are vast (e.g., Rattan et al., 2015). However, relatively little research has investigated intelligence mindsets in relation

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

to group-level educational disparities. We theorize that these mindsets may be particularly relevant in shaping how people make sense of racial and socioeconomic educational disparities because they provide a framework for inferring what is intellectually or academically possible for students from different racial and socioeconomic backgrounds. People who endorse fixed intelligence mindsets may interpret racial and socioeconomic disparities as reflections of differences in the innate, unchangeable intellectual abilities of students from different backgrounds. That is, regardless of cultural stereotypes or the specific patterns of disparities (e.g., which student groups outperform others), people who endorse fixed intelligence mindsets are likely to interpret educational disparities as indicating that the distribution of intelligence is such that students from certain groups simply have greater intellectual ability than students from other groups, and there is little that can or should be done to change that distribution of intelligence or the performance related disparities this distribution produces. Through the lens of a growth intelligence mindset, however, people may interpret racial and socioeconomic educational disparities as changeable realities. With sufficient resources and good strategies, these individuals may believe that low-performing students can grow their intelligence, and thus that educational disparities are malleable.

Building on this theorizing, we hypothesize that, because intelligence mindsets provide an interpretive lens for inferring the malleability of academic outcomes, they are likely to shape what, if anything, people believe should be done to address educational disparities. When people endorse fixed intelligence mindsets, we hypothesize that they will be more likely to endorse ideas and policies that sustain the status quo and reject ideas and policies that aim to change the status quo, such as through redistribution of educational resources. These

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

individuals are likely to believe that efforts to change the status quo will be ineffective in improving outcomes for low-performing students, who are destined to struggle as a result of their lower levels of intelligence. They may even perceive change efforts as being unfair to higher performing students, who could lose educational resources under redistributive policies. When people endorse growth intelligence mindsets, however, we hypothesize that they will be more likely to endorse ideas and policies that aim to change the status quo. From their perspective, it is possible that low-performing students can improve, and thus it may be possible to reduce achievement gaps by redistributing resources to support lower performing groups.

1.3 Theoretical Support

Both the mindsets literature and the system justification literature provide support for this theorizing. First, although much of the mindsets literature focuses on how mindsets shape interpretation of events involving individuals (e.g., academic success or failure; positive or negative behavior), these mindsets also have implications for individuals' preferences for society more broadly. Chiu et al. (1997), for example, found that people who endorsed a fixed mindset about their socio-moral reality (i.e., beliefs about the world and people's character as fixed or unchangeable entities) were more supportive of morality systems that maintained the status quo by enforcing strict rules and punishing deviance. People who endorsed a growth mindset about their socio-moral reality, however, were more supportive of morality systems that allowed for individual change, growth, and rehabilitation into society.

Recent research also illustrates that mindsets shape people's preferences for policies that would maintain versus change the status quo in terms of supporting culturally and

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

economically marginalized members of society. In one series of studies, people who endorsed fixed mindsets about whether people can change the kind of person they are (i.e., kind of person mindsets) were less supportive of immigration policies that provided support for resettling refugees, as they believed refugees would be unlikely to assimilate into their society (Madan et al., 2019). Similarly, people who endorsed fixed intelligence mindsets were less likely to support policies to increase wages for low-wage workers, who are stereotyped as having relatively low levels of intellectual ability (Madan et al., 2023). These findings illustrate that when people believe that aspects of other people are relatively unchangeable, they are more likely to support existing policies and thus, in many cases, to preserve aspects of the existing social system that contribute to certain groups' marginalization. When people believe that others can change, however, they are more supportive of policies that would make a meaningful difference in the lives of those who are marginalized in society.

Importantly, the difference between people who endorse growth versus fixed mindsets is not necessarily in what information they take in about the world, but in how they make sense of this information and use it to determine the best course of action. For instance, Rattan and Dweck (2010) demonstrated that both people who endorsed fixed mindsets and those who endorsed growth mindsets recognized prejudicial behavior as being prejudicial. The difference emerged in how individuals responded to this social reality. People who endorsed a growth mindset were more likely to confront prejudicial behavior than people who endorsed a fixed mindset, who believed confronting prejudicial behavior was unlikely to make a difference. This research provides further evidence that endorsing a fixed mindset may predispose people to accepting (rather than questioning or challenging) the status quo.

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

Second, findings from the mindsets literature dovetail with another theory of how people make meaning of and respond to social events: system justification theory (Jost & Banaji, 1994; Jost et al., 2004; Jost & Hunyady, 2005). This theory contends that people are particularly likely to legitimize inequalities when they feel that systems that produce inequalities are unlikely to change (van der Toorn et al., 2015). This belief is akin to a fixed mindset, through which people interpret outcomes in life as the product of fixed, unchangeable characteristics of people and their social worlds (Hong et al., 1999). In many cases, legitimizing inequality looks less like vocal advocacy for unfair social systems and more like passive acceptance or lack of effort to change these systems. For example, like the participants in Rattan and Dweck's (2010) work who failed to confront prejudice because they believed that people are unlikely to change their prejudiced beliefs, individuals often legitimize unfair social systems by failing to support policies that would bring about action to remedy inequality and bring about more equitable social systems (Jost & Hunyady, 2005; Madan et al., 2019).

1.4 Current Research

In the current study, we examine whether fixed intelligence mindsets undermine efforts to change unequal social systems. We hypothesize that individuals who endorse a fixed intelligence mindset will: 1) more strongly endorse system legitimizing beliefs; 2) downplay educational institutions' responsibility in shaping student outcomes; 3) downplay the importance of considering race within educational contexts; and 4) offer less support for redistributive educational policies (i.e., policies that aim to create more equitable outcomes for students). Although it is theoretically possible that other types of mindsets, such as about the malleability personality (Dweck & Leggett, 1988) or choice (Savani & Rattan, 2012) predict

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

greater system legitimization, we focus on intelligence mindsets for two key reasons. First, these are among the most well-documented mindsets in the literature, with numerous empirical studies providing precedent for their measurement and predictive validity, particularly in educational contexts. Second, intelligence mindsets are directly related to how people interpret academic outcomes (e.g., Blackwell et al., 2007), which are at the heart of educational disparities. Thus, we theorized that intelligence mindsets would be predictive of legitimization of educational inequalities, given their relevance to the domain of education (e.g., Madan et al. 2019; c.f. Rattan et al., 2012). We test these hypotheses via a meta-analysis of 20 original studies with K-12 staff (i.e., teachers, administrators, and other district workers; $N \approx 2,001$), college student samples ($N \approx 2,725$), and American adults recruited via MTurk ($k = 5$; $N \approx 1,792$).

The first of these original studies were designed to explore how policies specifying different benchmarks for achievement for students from different racial backgrounds (e.g., O'Connor, 2012) shape the way people make sense of educational disparities (Student Studies 1-3). As reported in Table 3, none of the manipulations had the intended effects, and we ended this line of inquiry. However, we continued to explore relationships between mindsets and legitimization of educational inequalities in a separate line of work with K-12 teachers (Teacher Studies 1-8). As we developed the theory articulated in this paper, we pooled studies from the two lines of work to meta-analyze the relationships between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimization. To support this meta-analysis, we conducted an additional series of studies in which we attempted to manipulate mindsets and examine their effects on the legitimization of educational inequality (Student Studies 4, 6, and 7; Mturk Studies 1-5). Despite

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

using manipulations that were effective in prior work, and despite achieving sufficient power to detect effects, these manipulations also failed to achieve the intended effect.

Here, we report data from all studies in our file drawer in which we have a measure of intelligence mindsets and at least one measure of system legitimization (See Table 1 for sample sizes and study dates, Table 2 for measures contributed by each study). In line with previous research (e.g., Savani & Rattan, 2012), our conceptualization of system legitimization includes both attitudinal measures and policy preference measures. Integration of multiple measures of system legitimization allows for a relatively robust examination of the relationship between intelligence mindsets and system legitimizing beliefs and policy preferences. By meta-analyzing these data, we aim to contribute to an emerging body of literature illustrating how individuals' mindsets shape their preferences for society (e.g., Madan et al., 2019; Madan et al., 2020; Madan et al., 2023; Savani and Rattan, 2012).

2. Method

2.1 Studies Included

To test our hypotheses, we meta-analyzed data from 20 studies we conducted between 2013 and 2020. Eight studies included samples of K-12 staff from Washington state and Oregon, seven studies included undergraduate students from the University of Washington (see Table 1 for demographic characteristics of each study), and five studies included U.S. adults recruited through Mturk. For studies involving undergraduate students, we aimed to collect approximately 200 participants per condition. This was a commonly used heuristic at the time of data collection, following evidence that correlation coefficients stabilize around this number (Schönbrodt and Perugini, 2013). For studies involving K-12 staff, sample sizes were based on

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

convenience, as opposed to a strict sample size determination. That is, we included all subjects who enrolled in the studies during the recruitment timeframe. Four of the Mturk studies were pilot studies in which we aimed to recruit 50-100 participants, and one was a fully powered study in which we aimed to recruit a sample large enough to detect a small effect with .80 power. For the purpose of this meta-analysis, we include all subjects who completed an intelligence mindset measure and at least one other key measure reported in this study.

As noted above, some studies included in the meta-analyses were designed to test other research questions, and some studies included experimental manipulations of mindset, racial differences in educational opportunities/performance, or educational systems' responsibility for student outcomes ($k = 11$). By and large, these manipulations did not affect the key variables reported in this paper (see Table 3 for details). Only four manipulations yielded significant mean-level differences on mindset, although one of these was driven by the control condition. Furthermore, only two significant effects emerged based on condition; all other condition effects on the variables examined in this paper were non-significant. Therefore, in the primary analyses, we collapsed across conditions to examine the hypothesized relationships. For results disaggregated by condition, see Moderation Analyses in Results. All Supplementary Materials can be found at:

https://osf.io/zj8sw/?view_only=b785d513ac7247c19e68a49e3303374d.

2.2 Measures

Measures varied slightly across studies (i.e., the number of items used and exact wording of items), but all studies in the meta-analyses included a multi-item intelligence mindset scale and at least one of five measures of system legitimization. For each of these

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

measures, we calculated composites for participants who responded to at least 60% of scale items. The 60% response rate was our only exclusion criterion. Below, we describe each construct measured (See Supplementary Material for scale items).

2.2.1 Fixed versus growth intelligence mindsets. We measured endorsement of growth versus fixed intelligence mindsets using Likert scale items adapted from previous research (Dweck, 1999). Among student and Mturk samples, mindset scales assessed generalized beliefs about the malleability of intelligence (e.g., *People have a certain amount of intelligence and can't do much to change it*). Among teacher samples, scales assessed beliefs about the malleability of intelligence based on participants' teaching experience (e.g., *Although I like to believe that all students can increase their intellectual ability, my experience tells me that some students are more capable than others*). All mindset scales were reliable ($\alpha \geq .71$). In all samples, higher values were coded to indicate stronger endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets.

2.2.2 System legitimization. System legitimization broadly refers to a set of beliefs, ideologies, and actions that justify, maintain, and bolster the current social order (Jost and Major, 2001). For the purposes of this manuscript, system legitimization was operationalized in five ways: 1) endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, 2) shifting responsibility for student success away from educational institutions, 3) downplaying the importance of race in educational contexts, 4) support for race-conscious educational policies, and 5) support for redistributive educational policies. Below we describe each operationalization of system legitimization (See Tables 4.1 and 4.2 for correlations between measures of system legitimization).

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

2.2.2.1 Endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs. We measured system legitimizing beliefs (SLBs) using Likert scale items used in previous research (Levin et al., 1998). Specifically, participants indicated whether they agreed with four statements comprising the system legitimacy subscale of this measure, which assesses the extent to which people believe that differences between social groups in society are fair (e.g., *America is a just society where differences in status between groups reflect actual group differences*). This measure showed adequate reliability across studies (in one study $\alpha = .55$; however, in all other studies $\alpha \geq .62$). In all samples, higher values were coded to indicate stronger endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs.

2.2.2.2 Perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes. Across five questions, we measured the extent to which people believe that schools (i.e., educational systems), teachers, parents, and students are responsible for various positive and negative student outcomes. Rather than assessing explicit system legitimizing beliefs, this measure captures a subtler system legitimizing tendency: shifting responsibility away from the educational system and toward individuals within that system. For example, one item asked, *When a student struggles academically, who is responsible for improving the student's performance?* Participants responded by assigning a percentage of responsibility (out of 100%) to teachers, parents, students, and schools. In this meta-analysis, we only focus on attributions of responsibility to schools. We averaged across responses to the five questions to create a composite variable measuring attributions of institutional (school) responsibility. In all studies, this measure was reliable (all $\alpha \geq .85$). Higher values indicated attributing greater responsibility to schools for student outcomes; therefore, higher values indicate *less* system legitimization.

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

2.2.2.3 Downplaying the importance of student race. We measured the extent to which people believe that educational contexts should acknowledge students' racial backgrounds (e.g., *Given the diversity of students in school, teachers should downplay and ignore racial and ethnic differences*; 1 = Strongly Disagree 7 = Strongly Agree). Prior research demonstrates that one way people legitimize racial inequality is by downplaying the importance of race in shaping individuals' outcomes, or by "taking race off the table" when discussing equity issues (Chow & Knowles, 2016; Neville et al., 2013). By failing to acknowledge racial differences and thus not allowing for discussion of racial inequality in treatment or resources, people allow the systems that create these differences to persist and thus legitimize these systems. In all studies, this scale was reliable (in one study $\alpha = .53$; however, in all other studies $\alpha \geq .72$). Higher values indicated a greater tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts; therefore, higher values indicate greater system legitimization.

2.2.2.4 Support for race-conscious educational policies. We measured the extent to which people support race-conscious educational policies (e.g., a proposal to provide free additional test preparation materials to schools serving racial minority/low-income communities; 1 = Strongly Oppose, 7 = Strongly Support). This measure assesses behavioral intentions to engage in system legitimization (i.e., by opposing educational policies that would explicitly consider race in order to create more equitable outcomes). In all studies, this scale was reliable ($\alpha \geq .80$). Higher values indicated greater support for race-conscious educational policies; therefore, higher values indicate *less* system legitimization.

2.2.2.5 Support for redistributive educational policies. Our final measure of system legitimization assessed support for three redistributive educational policies (e.g., a pooled

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

property tax distributed to school districts based on student enrollment and cost of living; 1 = Strongly Oppose, 7 = Strongly Support; Rattan et al., 2012). This measure assesses behavioral intentions to engage in system legitimization (i.e., by opposing policies that would change the educational system to create more equitable outcomes). In all studies, this scale was reliable (in one study $\alpha = .55$; however, in all other studies $\alpha s \geq .65$). Higher values indicated greater support for redistributive educational policies; therefore, higher values indicate *less* system legitimization.

2.3 Analytic Approach

Our primary analyses included five meta-analyses that examined the relations between fixed intelligence mindsets and each measure of system legitimization. We used the *metafor* package in *R* to calculate both fixed and random effects using Pearson's *r* values. Fixed effects models estimate the average effect for studies included in each meta-analysis and thus represent a descriptive statistic. Random effects models estimate the average effect for studies in general and thus represent an inferential statistic about the generalizability of meta-analytic findings (Borenstein et al., 2010; Goh et al., 2016). For ease of interpretation, we present the results of random effects models in text, along with the confidence intervals and the measure of effect size heterogeneity (*Q*). For the results of fixed effect models, see Table 5.

3. Results

3.1 Primary Analyses

Across all meta-analyses, we found support for the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization. Greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, $r(N = 2974)$

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

= .21, $k = 8$, $z = 6.31$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.14, .27], $Q = 19.84$ (see Figure 1); less perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $r(N = 3,901) = -.15$, $k = 13$, $z = 7.71$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.19, -.11], $Q = 10.42$ (see Figure 2); a stronger tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts, $r(N = 4494) = .24$, $k = 14$, $z = 3.29$, $p = .001$, 95% CI [.10, .39], $Q = 315.50$ (see Figure 3); less support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 2,361) = -.17$, $k = 9$, $z = 5.47$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.23, -.11], $Q = 15.29$ (see Figure 4); and less support for redistributive educational policies, $r(N = 1792) = -.15$, $k = 5$, $z = 2.80$, $p = .005$, 95% CI [-.25, -.04], $Q = 9.06$ (see Figure 5).

3.2 Moderation Analyses

Given the diversity of samples and study designs, we also conducted exploratory moderation analyses to examine whether the relationships between fixed intelligence mindsets and each of the system legitimizing outcomes varied as a function of participants' race, gender, or socioeconomic status (i.e., working class vs. middle class) or as a function of the study design (i.e., whether the relationship was assessed after an experimental manipulation). Below, we report the overarching results from these analyses. See Supplementary Material for forest plots.

3.2.1 Race. We used a two-pronged approach to examine whether the relationship between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimization varied by participants' racial background. First, we split the data file for each study by race (i.e., White, Asian, Black, Latino/a, and "Another Racial/Ethnic Identity," which primarily included multiracial people; we did not have enough Native American or Middle Eastern participants to estimate effects for these groups) and conducted five meta-analyses that paralleled the primary analyses for each

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

racial group. Second, to examine whether the relationships between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimizing outcomes differed across racial groups, we constructed a meta-regression model to compare the strength of each meta-analytic effect across racial groups. In these models, race (at the sample level) was dummy coded (White was the reference category) as the moderator of interest. Because the racial composition of studies varied, meta-regression models ranged from $k = 21$ to $k = 51$.

3.2.1.1 White participants. All meta-analyses supported the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization among White participants. Specifically, greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, $r(N = 1402) = .17$, $k = 8$, $z = 6.50$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.12, .23], $Q = 20.05$ (see Figure S1); less perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $r(N = 2631) = -.14$, $k = 13$, $z = 7.03$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.18, -.09], $Q = 7.60$ (see Figure S2); a stronger tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts, $r(N = 3140) = .23$, $k = 14$, $z = 12.77$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.19, .26], $Q = 155.13$ (see Figure S3); less support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 1247) = -.17$, $k = 9$, $z = 6.05$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.23, -.12], $Q = 11.29$ (see Figure S4); and less support for redistributive educational policies, $r(N = 1194) = -.15$, $k = 5$, $z = 5.13$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.20, -.09], $Q = 1.58$ (see Figure S5).

3.2.1.2 Asian participants. Three of five meta-analyses supported the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization among Asian participants. Specifically, greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, $r(N = 939) = .21$, $k = 7$, $z = 6.32$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.14, .27], $Q = 7.51$ (see Figure S1); a stronger tendency to downplay the importance of race

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

within educational contexts, $r(N = 342) = .31$, $k = 8$, $z = 5.70$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.21, .40], $Q = 15.34$ (see Figure S3); and less support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 635) = -.24$, $k = 6$, $z = 6.16$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.32, -.17], $Q = 8.14$ (see Figure S4). Although in the predicted direction, the relationship between fixed intelligence mindsets and perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes was only marginally statistically significant, $r(N = 282) = -.11$, $k = 7$, $z = 1.77$, $p = .076$, 95% CI [-.23, .01], $Q = 3.01$ (see Figure S2). Endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets did not predict support for redistributive educational policies among Asian participants, $r(N = 58) = -.16$, $k = 2$, $z = 1.19$, $p = .232$, 95% CI [-.41, .11], $Q = 1.02$ (see Figure S5); however, only two studies contributed to this analysis.

3.2.1.3 Black participants. Two of five meta-analyses supported the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization among Black participants. Specifically, greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted less perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $r(N = 361) = -.23$, $k = 6$, $z = 4.38$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.33, -.13], $Q = 9.13$ (see Figure S2) and less support for redistributive educational policies, $r(N = 351) = -.33$, $k = 5$, $z = 6.29$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.42, -.23], $Q = 2.10$ (see Figure S5). Endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets did not significantly predict endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, although the relationship was in the predicted direction, $r(N = 51) = .22$, $k = 6$, $z = 1.29$, $p = .196$, 95% CI [-.12, .51], $Q = 3.26$ (see Figure S1) or support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 77) = -.04$, $k = 8$, $z = .26$, $p = .795$, 95% CI [-.31, .24], $Q = 9.23$ (see Figure S4). Notably, however, the number of Black participants in the studies included in these meta-analyses was small, resulting in less power to detect effects of mindsets on these two operationalizations of system legitimization. Finally, and unexpectedly, greater endorsement of

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

fixed intelligence mindsets predicted a *decreased* tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts, $r(N = 362) = -.34$, $k = 6$, $z = 6.60$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.43, -.25], $Q = 19.07$ (see Figure S3).

3.2.1.4 Latino/a participants. Two of five meta-analyses supported the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization among Latino/a participants. Specifically, greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, $r(N = 119) = .43$, $k = 7$, $z = 4.57$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.26, .58], $Q = 12.55$ (see Figure S1); and a stronger tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts, $r(N = 239) = .29$, $k = 10$, $z = 4.33$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.16, .41], $Q = 16.73$ (see Figure S3). Endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets did not significantly predict perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $r(N = 240) = .013$, $k = 10$, $z = .19$, $p = .851$, 95% CI [-.12, .15], $Q = 4.69$ (see Figure S2); support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 58) = .07$, $k = 7$, $z = .44$, $p = .659$, 95% CI [-.24, .38], $Q = 4.01$ (see Figure S4); or support for redistributive educational policies, although this pattern of results was in the predicted direction, $r(N = 88) = -.13$, $k = 4$, $z = 1.14$, $p = .254$, 95% CI [-.34, .09], $Q = 1.03$ (see Figure S5). Notably, however, the studies contributing to the last two meta-analyses included small samples of Latino/a participants, resulting in less power to detect effects of mindsets on these operationalizations of system legitimization.

3.2.1.5 Participants from Another Racial/Ethnic Background. All meta-analyses supported the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization among participants from “Another racial/ethnic background.” Specifically, greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater endorsement of system

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

legitimizing beliefs, $r(N = 390) = .24$, $k = 8$, $z = 4.68$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.14, .34], $Q = 7.99$ (see Figure S1); less perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes (marginally), $r(N = 269) = -.12$, $k = 13$, $z = 1.90$, $p = .057$, 95% CI [-.25, .004], $Q = 7.08$ (see Figure S2); a stronger tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts, $r(N = 270) = .35$, $k = 13$, $z = 5.48$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.23, .45], $Q = 18.40$ (see Figure S3); less support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 296) = -.20$, $k = 9$, $z = 3.34$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.31, -.08], $Q = 8.68$ (see Figure S4); and less support for redistributive educational policies, $r(N = 80) = -.28$, $k = 5$, $z = 2.33$, $p = .020$, 95% CI [-.49, -.05], $Q = 11.76$ (see Figure S5).

Overall, the hypothesized relationship between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimizing outcomes consistently emerged among White participants and participants from “Another racial/ethnic background” (who were primarily multiracial individuals), for whom the associations between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimization were positive and statistically significant across all five meta-analyses. This relationship emerged somewhat less consistently among Asian participants, who demonstrated significant effects in the predicted direction across three out of five meta-analyses. The hypothesized relationship emerged least frequently among Black and Latino participants, who each demonstrated significant effects in the predicted direction across two out of five meta-analyses; however, these non-significant findings may have been driven by small sample sizes of Black and Latino participants.

3.2.1.6 Comparing racial groups. Despite some variation in the significance of the hypothesized relationships among Asian, Black, and Latino/a participants, meta-regression analyses examining participant race as a moderator of the relationship between mindsets and system legitimizing outcomes revealed few significant differences between racial groups. The

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

relationships between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimizing beliefs, $QM(df = 4) = 8.30, p = .081$; perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $QM(df = 4) = 8.36, p = .079$; or support for race-conscious educational policies, $QM(df = 4) = 6.12, p = .190$ did not differ for White participants relative to Black, Asian, Latino/a participants, or participants from “Another racial/ethnic background.”

One significant omnibus effect indicated that participant race moderated the extent to which fixed intelligence mindsets predicted support for redistributive educational policies, $QM(df = 4) = 10.75, p = .030$. However, probing analyses suggested that this effect was primarily driven by a significant difference in the strength of the relationship for White relative to Black participants, $z = 3.13, p = .002$. Among both groups, the relationship was positive and significant. Thus, despite the significant omnibus test, the results suggest that participants from different racial groups did not differ in a way that contradicts our hypothesis.

A second significant omnibus effect indicated that participant race moderated the extent to which fixed intelligence mindsets predicted the tendency to downplay the importance of race in educational contexts, $QM(df = 4) = 121.50, p < .001$. Probing analyses indicated that this effect was driven by a significant difference in relationship for White relative to Black participants, $z = 10.30, p < .001$: White participants demonstrated a significant positive relationship, while Black participants demonstrated a significant negative relationship.

3.2.1.7 Summary of race moderation analyses. Taken together, although analyses conducted individually by racial group reveal some variation in the extent to which fixed intelligence mindsets predict system legitimization, we caution against strong interpretation of these patterns, particularly for Black and Latino/a participants, given the relatively small sample

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

sizes. Only two comparisons between White and Black participants reached statistical significance, and in one of these instances, both groups demonstrated the hypothesized effect, albeit to differing degrees. In the other instance, the difference was driven by the negative association between fixed intelligence mindsets and downplaying race in educational settings that emerged for Black participants. This difference could indicate that downplaying race in educational settings carries a different meaning for Black relative to White participants, considering that Black participants' endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater system legitimization across other outcomes, much as these mindsets did for White participants and participants from other racial backgrounds.

3.2.2 Gender. To examine whether the relationship between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimization varied by participants' gender, we used the same two-pronged approach used to examine effects by participants' race. First, we split each data file by gender (i.e., male or female; we did not have enough participants who identified as "Another Gender Identity" to estimate effects for this group) and conducted meta-analyses that paralleled the primary analyses for male and female participants. Second, to examine whether the relationships between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimizing outcomes differed across gender, we constructed a meta-regression model to compare the strength of effects.

3.2.2.1. Female participants. All meta-analyses supported the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization among female participants. Specifically, greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, $r(N = 1920) = .21$, $k = 8$, $z = 9.20$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.16, .25], $Q = 12.76$ (see Figure S6); less perceived institutional responsibility for student

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

outcomes, $r(N = 2468) = -.14$, $k = 13$, $z = 6.77$, $p < .002$, 95% CI $[-.18, -.10]$, $Q = 2.86$ (see Figure S7); $r(N = 2688) = .28$, $k = 14$, $z = 14.81$, $p < .001$, 95% CI $[.24, .31]$, $Q = 136.04$ (see Figure S8); less support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 1406) = -.22$, $k = 9$, $z = 8.32$, $p < .001$, 95% CI $[-.27, -.17]$, $Q = 11.01$ (see Figure S9); and less support for redistributive educational policies, $r(N = 900) = -.19$, $k = 5$, $z = 5.10$, $p < .001$, 95% CI $[-.26, -.12]$, $Q = 7.19$ (see Figure S10).

3.2.2.2 Male participants. Four of five meta-analyses supported the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization among male participants. Specifically, greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, $r(N = 1031) = .19$, $k = 8$, $z = 6.05$, $p < .001$, 95% CI $[.13, .25]$, $Q = 6.10$ (see Figure S6); less perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $r(N = 1574) = -.16$, $k = 13$, $z = 6.41$, $p < .001$, 95% CI $[-.21, -.11]$, $Q = 22.39$ (see Figure S7); less support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 942) = -.15$, $k = 9$, $z = 4.68$, $p < .001$, 95% CI $[-.22, -.09]$, $Q = 6.17$ (see Figure S9); and less support for redistributive educational policies, $r(N = 1079) = -.21$, $k = 5$, $z = 6.89$, $p < .001$, 95% CI $[-.26, -.15]$, $Q = 6.91$ (see Figure S10). Greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets did not significantly predict tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts, $r(N = 1701) = .04$, $k = 14$, $z = 1.49$, $p = .137$, 95% CI $[-.01, .08]$, $Q = 122.68$ (see Figure S8).

3.2.2.3 Comparing male and female participants. Meta-regression analyses examining participant gender as a moderator of the relationship between mindsets and system legitimizing outcomes revealed only one significant difference: the extent to which fixed intelligence mindsets predicted the tendency to downplay the importance of race in educational contexts, $QM(df = 1) = 64.45$, $p < .001$. Among female participants the relationship

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

was positive and significant, and among male participants, the relationship was non-significant. The relationships between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimizing beliefs, $QM(df = 1) = .28, p = .598$; perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $QM(df = 1) = .36, p = .551$; or support for race-conscious educational policies, $QM(df = 1) = 2.63, p = .105$; or support for redistributive educational policies, $QM(df = 1) = .11, p = .738$ did not differ between male and female participants.

3.2.2.4 Summary of gender moderation analyses. Taken together, for both male and female participants, fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater system legitimization, as hypothesized. Only one difference emerged in the magnitude of this relationship: the relationship between fixed intelligence mindset and the tendency to downplay the importance of race in educational contexts was significant for female participants but non-significant for male participants.

3.2.3 Socioeconomic status. As with the race and gender moderation analyses, we took a two-pronged approach to examine whether the relationship between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimization varied by participants' socioeconomic status (SES). First, we split the data file for each study by SES and conducted five meta-analyses that paralleled the primary analyses for working-class and middle-class participants. Working-class was defined as either having less than a 4-year college degree for the Teacher and MTurk samples, or as both parents having less than a 4-year college degree for Student Samples. Middle-class was defined as having at least a 4-year college degree for the Teacher and MTurk samples, or as having at least 1 parent with a 4-year college degree for Student Samples. Second, to examine whether the relationships between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimizing outcomes

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

differed across SES, we constructed a meta-regression model to compare the strength of effects for working- and middle-class participants.

3.2.3.1 Working-class participants. All meta-analyses supported the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization among working-class participants. Specifically, greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, $r(N = 599) = .18$, $k = 7$, $z = 4.33$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.10, .26], $Q = 4.58$ (see Figure S11); less perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $r(N = 795) = -.08$, $k = 8$, $z = 2.18$, $p = .030$, 95% CI [-.15, -.001], $Q = 8.92$ (see Figure S12); a stronger tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts $r(N = 950) = .22$, $k = 10$, $z = 7.25$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.16, .27], $Q = 22.92$ (see Figure S13); less support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 568) = -.27$, $k = 9$, $z = 6.48$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.35, -.19], $Q = 6.22$ (see Figure S14); and less support for redistributive educational policies, $r(N = 612) = -.19$, $k = 5$, $z = 4.63$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.26, -.11], $Q = .33$ (see Figure S15).

3.2.3.2 Middle-class participants. All meta-analyses supported the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization among middle-class participants. Specifically, greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, $r(N = 2003) = .23$, $k = 7$, $z = 10.29$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.19, .27], $Q = 18.44$ (see Figure S11); less perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $r(N = 3045) = -.17$, $k = 13$, $z = 9.22$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.20, -.13], $Q = 16.98$ (see Figure S12); a stronger tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts, $r(N = 3459) = .14$, $k = 13$, $z = 7.59$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.10, .17], $Q = 277.60$ (see Figure S13); less support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 1789) = -.17$, $k = 9$, $z = 7.28$, $p < .001$, 95%

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

CI [-.22, -.13], $Q = 19.51$ (see Figure S14); and less support for redistributive educational policies $r(N = 1180) = .20$, $k = 5$, $z = 6.80$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.25, -.14], $Q = 11.81$ (see Figure S15).

3.2.3.3 Comparing working- and middle-class participants. Meta-regression analyses examining participant gender as a moderator of the relationship between mindsets and system legitimizing outcomes revealed three significant differences. Working- and middle-class participants differed in the extent to which fixed intelligence mindsets predicted perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $QM(df = 1) = 4.45$, $p = .026$); the tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts, $QM(df = 1) = 5.43$, $p = .020$; and support for race-conscious educational policies, $QM(df = 1) = 4.56$, $p = .033$. Despite these significant differences, however, the patterns of results were significant and in the predicted direction for both working- and middle-class participants, they were simply stronger among working-class compared to middle-class participants. The relationships between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimizing beliefs, $QM(df = 1) = 1.18$, $p = .278$; and support for redistributive educational policies, $QM(df = 1) = .04$, $p = .844$ did not differ by SES.

3.2.3.4 Summary of SES moderation analyses. Taken together, for both working- and middle-class participants, fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater system legitimization, as predicted. When significant differences arose, they were driven by a difference of magnitude rather than by the absence of a significant relationship.

3.2.4 Study design. As with the prior moderation analyses, we used a two-pronged approach to examine whether the relationship between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimization varied according to whether variables of interest were measured after a manipulation. First, for experimental studies, we split the data files by condition and pooled

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

these split files with the data from correlational studies. We categorized whether a given sample measured the variables of interest after an experimental manipulation. Samples that did not measure variables of interest after a manipulation were either originally correlational studies or no-information control conditions within experimental studies. We conducted five meta-analyses that paralleled the primary analyses for both types of samples. Second, we constructed a meta-regression model to compare the strength of effects across sample types.

3.2.4.1 Samples without a manipulation. All meta-analyses supported the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization. Specifically, greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, $r(N = 556) = .22$, $k = 3$, $z = 5.23$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.14, .30], $Q = 4.74$ (see Figure S16); less perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $r(N = 1815) = -.15$, $k = 11$, $z = 6.19$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.19, -.10], $Q = 4.58$ (see Figure S17); a stronger tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts, $r(N = 2380) = .33$, $k = 11$, $z = 16.45$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.29, .36], $Q = 127.54$ (see Figure S18); less support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 376) = -.15$, $k = 5$, $z = 2.92$, $p = .004$, 95% CI [-.25, -.05], $Q = 5.20$ (see Figure S19); and less support for redistributive educational policies, $r(N = 578) = -.24$, $k = 5$, $z = 5.92$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-.32, -.17], $Q = 2.61$ (see Figure S20).

3.2.4.2 Samples with an experimental manipulation. Four of five meta-analyses supported the hypothesis that endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicts system legitimization. Specifically, greater endorsement of fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater endorsement of system legitimizing beliefs, $r(N = 2227) = .22$, $k = 14$, $z = 10.65$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.18, .26], $Q = 12.17$ (see Figure S16); less perceived institutional responsibility for

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

student outcomes, $r(N = 2084) = -.16$, $k = 16$, $z = 7.24$, $p < .001$, 95% CI $[-.20, -.12]$, $Q = 30.18$ (see Figure S17); a stronger tendency to downplay the importance of race within educational contexts, $r(N = 2112) = .05$, $k = 17$, $z = 2.23$, $p = .025$, 95% CI $[.01, .10]$, $Q = 108.69$ (see Figure S18); less support for race-conscious educational policies, $r(N = 1776) = -.22$, $k = 22$, $z = 9.57$, $p < .001$, 95% CI $[-.26, -.17]$, $Q = 20.38$ (see Figure S19); and less support for redistributive educational policies, $r(N = 1214) = -.19$, $k = 11$, $z = 6.53$, $p < .001$, 95% CI $[-.24, -.13]$, $Q = 13.00$ (see Figure S20).

3.2.4.3 Comparing effects by sample type. Meta-regression analyses examining sample type as a moderator of the relationship between mindsets and system legitimizing outcomes revealed only one significant difference: the extent to which fixed intelligence mindsets predicted the tendency to downplay the importance of race in educational contexts was stronger among studies that did not measure the relationship after the manipulation, $QM(df = 1) = 92.47$, $p < .001$. Nonetheless, the relationship was significant for both types of samples. The relationships between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimizing beliefs, $QM(df = 1) = .01$, $p = .930$; perceived institutional responsibility for student outcomes, $QM(df = 1) = .19$, $p = .666$; or support for race-conscious educational policies, $QM(df = 1) = 1.28$, $p = .258$; or support for redistributive educational policies, $QM(df = 1) = 1.33$, $p = .249$ did not differ by sample type.

3.2.4.4 Summary of study design moderation analyses. Taken together, fixed intelligence mindsets predicted greater system legitimization in line with our hypothesis, regardless of whether the relationship was measured after an experimental manipulation.

4. Discussion

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

Across five measures of system legitimization, we found support for the hypothesis that fixed intelligence mindsets serve a system legitimizing function in educational contexts. Specifically, the more people endorsed a fixed intelligence mindset, the more they: 1) endorsed broad system legitimizing beliefs, 2) downplayed the responsibility of educational institutions in shaping student outcomes, 3) downplayed the importance of considering race within the educational contexts, 4) withheld support for race-conscious educational policies, and 5) withheld support for redistributive educational policies. Thus, in terms of both abstract (i.e., system legitimizing beliefs) and contextualized (i.e., perceived responsibility of educational institutions, perceived importance of student race, and support for race-conscious and redistributive educational policies) measures of system legitimization, fixed intelligence mindsets predicted stronger system legitimizing attitudes and behavioral intentions regarding support for educational policies.

Moderation analyses examining these relationships across participants from different racial, gender, and socioeconomic backgrounds revealed few significant differences, suggesting that the effects observed in the primary meta-analyses are relatively robust. No consistent differences emerged for male compared to female or working-class compared to middle-class participants, who all demonstrated the hypothesized effects. Only variations in the effects across racial groups provided evidence that further investigation could be informative. Although Black and Latino/a, and, to some extent, Asian participants demonstrated the hypothesized effect somewhat less consistently than White participants and multiracial participants, these variations often appeared to be driven by small sample sizes. Small sample sizes and a lack of statistical significance in comparisons warrant caution in generalizing from

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

observed variations in the effect among Black, Latino/a, and Asian participants relative to White participants. However, to the extent that these variations are replicable in larger samples, it is possible that the greater consistency in the relationship between fixed mindsets and system legitimization among White participants is driven in part by racially motivated reasoning. That is, when making sense of racial disparities in educational outcomes, White participants may consciously or unconsciously filter the issue through the lens of race. Internalized racial stereotypes and a motivation to maintain a positive self-image (Cole, 2018) may predispose White individuals to make meaning of their group's advantage by drawing upon fixed mindsets system legitimizing beliefs.

It is also notable that the relation between fixed mindset and system legitimization held even when participants were primed with educational inequality. Specifically, in Student Study 6, participants were asked to imagine that they were an elementary school teacher, and they were given information demonstrating that White and Asian students performed better than Latino and African American students (see Supplementary Material). In an open-ended manipulation check, many participants noted this racial disparity, suggesting that the manipulation made educational inequality salient. Although this study needs to be replicated to draw strong conclusions, it suggests that the relation between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimization does not depend upon the belief (or illusion) that current educational systems produce equal outcomes for students from different backgrounds. Instead, this relation may exist both in the presence and absence of information about educational inequality, much as Rattan and Dweck (2010) demonstrated that the relation between fixed mindsets and a reluctance to confront prejudice persisted even when people recognized

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

behavior as being prejudicial. Moreover, our moderation analyses revealed that the hypothesized link between fixed intelligence mindset and system legitimization emerged in samples that assessed the relationship after experimental primes designed to make educational inequality salient, and the strength of these relationships did not differ from those observed in samples that assessed the relationships without such manipulations.

4.1 Limitations and Future Directions

Although the meta-analyses provide strong evidence of the relationship between fixed intelligence mindsets and system legitimization, they rely on correlational data. Therefore, we cannot conclude that mindsets have a causal effect on efforts to change (or maintain) unequal educational systems. It is possible that the relations between fixed mindset and the various measures of system legitimization arise from a larger worldview about race, intelligence, and social structures. In fact, eight of the studies included in the meta-analyses attempted to manipulate college students' ($k = 3$) and American adults' ($k = 5$) mindsets to examine the causal effect of fixed mindset on system legitimization (see Supplementary Material), but these manipulations did not produce reliable results. Only two of these studies demonstrated the intended effect on mindsets, even when the manipulations proved effective in prior published literature. Moreover, a third study demonstrated a contrary significant effect: the manipulation led to *greater* endorsement of fixed mindset in both the fixed and growth mindset conditions compared to the control condition. This failure to manipulate mindset could suggest that mindsets are deeply rooted elements of people's worldviews that are particularly difficult to change, or that certain parameters must be met in order to change individuals' mindsets (see Dweck & Yeager, 2019). Further research is needed to understand both the parameters under

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

which mindsets can be manipulated and the causal effects of mindsets on social and ideological beliefs such as system legitimacy.

With the current research, we are also unable to discern whether fixed intelligence mindsets (as opposed to fixed mindsets in general) are uniquely predictive of system legitimization in educational contexts. We anticipated that fixed intelligence mindsets would be particularly influential in shaping individuals' beliefs about educational policies due to their domain specificity in educational contexts (e.g., Madan et al., 2019), but we did not systematically measure other mindsets with which we can compare the effects of fixed intelligence mindsets. Two studies included in this meta-analysis assessed one other mindset: non-universal (versus universal) beliefs about intelligence, or the belief that only some people, as opposed to all people, have the capacity to become highly intelligent. Rattan et al. (2012) demonstrated that non-universal beliefs about intelligence were only modestly correlated with intelligence mindsets and were uniquely predictive of decreased support for redistributive educational policies. In our studies, however, these beliefs were highly correlated with intelligence mindsets and showed inconsistent relationships with similar system legitimizing measures as those used in Rattan and colleagues' research (see Supplementary Material). Given the limited data available in our studies, we cannot draw strong conclusions about the unique predictive validity of fixed intelligence mindsets. However, this divergence from previous research on non-universal beliefs about intelligence suggests that further inquiry may be warranted.

Because these meta-analyses include teacher, student, and adult samples, they suggest that the tendency to legitimize inequality is not restricted to people who are employed by—and

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

thus have a stake in upholding—the educational systems that create racially unequal outcomes in the U.S. Teacher, student, and Mturk samples all demonstrated a clear and generally consistent relation between fixed mindsets about intelligence and system legitimization. Yet, future research is needed to explore how the relation between mindsets and system legitimization changes depend upon one's role in the school system (e.g., comparing policy makers, teachers, students, and families from different backgrounds). Similarly, examining ideological and psychological moderators such as political orientation, internal vs. external motivations to control prejudice, and perceived efficacy to create system change will shed light on the parameters of the relationships observed in our meta-analyses. A more nuanced examination of potential moderators of this effect will clarify how, when, and for whom fixed mindset is likely to play a system legitimizing role in educational contexts. Another possibility is that this relation generalizes to other domains and thus could be important in understanding why inequality persists in other domains. For example, Madan et al. (2019) demonstrated that fixed mindsets undermine individuals' support for refugee resettlement, as people who endorse a fixed mindset believed that refugees would be less able to assimilate to mainstream society. In effect, a fixed mindset led individuals to maintain the status quo by excluding refugees. Similar relations may exist in other consequential domains where people from different racial and socioeconomic backgrounds face disparate outcomes, such as housing, health care, and employment.

4.2 Constraints on Generality

Given the racial-ethnic, gender, and social class diversity of our samples, as well as the different means of recruitment used in this research, we anticipate that the findings are likely

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

to generalize to similarly diverse samples. However, further research is needed to provide a more nuanced understanding of how the relations reported here vary both across and within groups. We found limited evidence that racial demographics shaped the relationships reported in this paper; however, research with larger samples of racially minoritized participants will allow for a fuller exploration of the generality of findings across racial groups. We also anticipate that findings will replicate with similar measures of mindsets and system legitimization (i.e., both abstract measures and those contextualized in education). Because the data were collected over a span of seven years, with significant social and political changes occurring during this time (e.g., the transition from the Obama administration to the Trump administration), we do not have reason to believe that these findings are temporally-bound. However, as the U.S. continues to reckon with widespread racial inequalities in key societal institutions (e.g., policing, criminal justice, education; Pasquerella, 2020; United Nations, 2021), it is theoretically possible that beliefs about intelligence, particularly racialized beliefs (e.g., certain groups are more intelligent than others), and system legitimacy will shift such that people will be less likely to endorse fixed views of intelligence or uphold inequitable educational systems. We are not aware of other factors that may influence the generality of our findings.

5. Conclusion

Together, meta-analyses from 20 studies including K-12 staff, college students and U.S. adults demonstrate that people who endorse fixed mindsets about intelligence are more likely to legitimize educational inequality than those who endorse growth mindsets. These findings suggest that fixed mindsets may play a role in perpetuating inequality by providing an

MINDSETS AND EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY

interpretive lens through which people accept the status quo as reflective of innate, unchangeable differences in the distribution of intelligence across race or social class. However, our findings also point to a potential path forward by leveraging growth mindsets to motivate individuals to both acknowledge and challenge educational inequalities.

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Table 1. Information about each study contributing to the meta-analysis.

Dashes (-) in cells denote that the study did not include the measure. Blank cells denote that the information is not applicable to study. Due to rounding, the percentages for race may not total 100%. * This value represents the average number of years participants have worked in the school district where data was collected. †This study was pre-registered.

Note. For studies that included an experimental manipulation, results are presented collapsing across the manipulation(s), see Table 3 for more detailed information about how manipulations affected participants’ responses.

Study #	Data Collection Initiated	N	Mean Age (SD)	Years of Teaching Experience (SD)	% Working Class	% Women	Racial Identification					
							% White	% Asian/Pacific Islander	% Black	% Latino/Hispanic	% Native American	% Multiracial/Other
Teacher Study 1	05/2017	293	-	14.39 (8.54)	17	78	72	1	0	17	1	9
Teacher Study 2	05/2018	263	-	15.17 (9.09)	1	78	75	0	0	14	1	10
Teacher Study 3	02/2012	264	45.26 (9.88)	15.12 (9.3)	0	75	87	2	1	1	3	7
Teacher Study 4	05/2016	78	-	-	0	94	72	12	0	9	0	6
Teacher Study 5	03/2017	100	-	-	1	86	77	7	2	2	3	8
Teacher Study 6	03/2018	104	-	-	0	92	71	8	1	6	2	12
Teacher Study 7	06/2015	597	-	12.38* (8.68)	30	79	90			10		

Study #	Data Collection Initiated	N	Mean Age (SD)	Years of Teaching Experience (SD)	% Working Class	% Women	Racial Identification					
							% White	% Asian/Pacific Islander	% Black	% Latino/Hispanic	% Native American	% Multiracial/Other
Teacher Study 8	04/2019	300	-	13.33 (8.99)	13	76	71	0	2	19	0	8
Student Study 1	01/2013	360	19.22 (2.11)		-	66	35	44	3	4	0	14
Student Study 2	04/2013	381	19.48 (1.48)		33	62	37	40	3	4	1	15
Student Study 3	01/2014	519	19.27 (2.20)		28	58	34	42	2	6	0	16
Student Study 4	05/2017	189	19.65 (1.50)		28	50	47	25	3	7	1	17
Student Study 5	04/2017	227	19.31 (2.52)		32	62	35	41	2	4	0	17
Student Study 6	01/2017	863	19.06 (1.63)		13	69	63	23	1	2	0	10
Student Study 7	10/2017	186	18.65 (1.44)		28	65	33	40	1	3	0	22
Mturk Study 1	1/2020	97	37.59 (11.94)		39	39	77	2	8	3	1	11

Study #	Data Collection Initiated	N	Mean Age (SD)	Years of Teaching Experience (SD)	% Working Class	% Women	Racial Identification					
							% White	% Asian/Pacific Islander	% Black	% Latino/Hispanic	% Native American	% Multiracial/Other
Mturk Study 2	1/2020	59	36.03 (10.34)		36	37	73	2	12	7	0	7
Mturk Study 3	2/2020	93	37.46 (11.75)		34	33	75	4	11	4	1	4
Mturk Study 4 [†]	2/2020	1398	35.86 (10.58)		34	39	64	4	22	5	0	4
Mturk Study 5	3/2020	145	35.23 (10.67)		32	48	75	2	12	3	1	7

Table 2. Information about measures from each study contributing to the meta-analyses.

^a Mindset was measured on a 7-point Likert scale in this study. ^b Mindset was measured on a 20-point sliding scale in these studies. All other studies used a 6-point Likert scale to measure mindset. Blank cells indicate that the measure was not included in the study.

Study #	Items of interest assessed after a manipulation	System Legitimization																	
		Fixed Mindset			System Legitimizing Beliefs			Perceived Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes			Perceived Importance of Student Race			Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies			Support for Redistributive Educational Policies		
		Items	M (SD)	α	Items	M (SD)	α	Items	M (SD)	α	Items	M (SD)	α	Items	M (SD)	α	Items	M (SD)	α
Teacher Study 1	No	6	2.74 (.86)	.73	4	2.51 (1.14)	.77	5	14.52 (9.82)	.93	4	2.08 (1.00)	.81						
Teacher Study 2	No	6	2.67 (.87)	.78				5	14.01 (8.01)	.86	4	1.94 (.95)	.83						
Teacher Study 3	No	5	3.07 ^a (1.19)	.73				5	13.30 (7.87)	.87	4	2.79 (1.08)	.72						
Teacher Study 4	No	6	2.25 (.77)	.80				5	15.91 (8.93)	.85	4	1.92 (.76)	.74						
Teacher Study 5	No	6	2.50 (.76)	.77				5	15.85 (11.96)	.92	4	2.04 (.92)	.77						
Teacher Study 6	No	6	2.42 (.72)	.81				5	16.43 (11.22)	.94	4	1.72 (.60)	.53						
Teacher Study 7	No	5	3.36 (1.08)	.71							4	3.21 (1.16)	.73						

System Legitimization

Study #	Items of interest assessed after a manipulation	System Legitimization																		
		Fixed Mindset			System Legitimizing Beliefs				Perceived Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes			Perceived Importance of Student Race			Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies			Support for Redistributive Educational Policies		
		Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α	Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α	Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α	Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α	Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α	Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α	
Teacher Study 8	No	6	2.59 (.83)	.77					5	14.45 (7.66)	.86	4	2.05 (.99)	.83						
Student Study 1	Yes	8	2.84 (.89)	.92	4	3.52 (.92)	.55													
Student Study 2	Yes	8	2.70 (.87)	.91	4	3.33 (.93)	.63													
Student Study 3	Yes	8	2.78 (.92)	.91	4	3.50 (.95)	.62						4	5.45 (1.12)	.83					
Student Study 4	Yes	8	2.93 (1.01)	.93	4	3.09 (1.08)	.76						4	5.67 (1.04)	.85					
Student Study 5	No	8	2.83 (.93)	.94	4	2.88 (.99)	.73						4	5.88 (.91)	.82					
Student Study 6	Yes	8	2.40 (.89)	.93	4	2.98 (1.01)	.74	5	13.69 (10.90)	.91	4	3.10 (1.22)	.76	4	6.12 (.85)	.83				
Student Study 7	Yes	8	2.82 (.94)	.93	4	2.81 (.99)	.68						4	5.95 (.92)	.81					
Mturk Study 1	Yes	1	8.48 ^b (5.54)					5	13.73 (9.20)	.83	4	3.54 (1.30)	.84	4	5.78 (1.13)	.80	3	4.31 (1.18)	.65	

System Legitimization

Study #	Items of interest assessed after a manipulation	System Legitimization																	
		Fixed Mindset			System Legitimizing Beliefs			Perceived Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes			Perceived Importance of Student Race			Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies			Support for Redistributive Educational Policies		
		Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α	Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α	Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α	Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α	Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α	Items	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	α
Mturk Study 2	Yes	1	9.14 ^b (5.95)				5	12.99 (8.72)	.83	4	3.67 (1.44)	.87	4	5.82 (1.09)	.85	3	4.19 (1.35)	.78	
Mturk Study 3	Yes	1	8.30 ^b (5.14)				5	13.56 (8.74)	.88	4	3.92 (1.19)	.85	4	5.61 (1.06)	.81	3	4.25 (1.16)	.73	
Mturk Study 4	Yes	1	7.61 ^b (4.95)				5	15.19 (9.40)	.85	4	3.82 (1.27)	.83				3	4.30 (1.13)	.65	
Mturk Study 5	Yes	8	3.45 (1.21)	.91			5	15.51 (8.96)	.85	4	3.73 (1.35)	.85	4	5.74 (1.07)	.84	3	4.50 (.98)	.56	

Condition	Fixed Mindset		System Legitimizing Beliefs		Perceived Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes		Perceived Importance of Student Race		Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies		Support for Redistributive Educational Policies	
	<i>M</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>F</i>
	(<i>SD</i>)		(<i>SD</i>)		(<i>SD</i>)		(<i>SD</i>)		(<i>SD</i>)		(<i>SD</i>)	

Student Study 3

Low Achievement Standards

Single Target Achievement Policy	2.66 (.72)		3.43 (.98)						5.48 (1.11)			
Race-Based Achievement Policy	2.77 (1.00)		3.46 (.97)						5.40 (1.11)			

High Achievement Standards

Single Target Achievement Policy	2.90 (1.00)		3.58 (.94)						5.46 (1.10)			
Race-Based Achievement Policy	2.79 (.95)		3.52 (.88)						5.48 (1.18)			

Effect of Condition		.60		.17						.008		
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Condition	Fixed Mindset		System Legitimizing Beliefs		Perceived Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes		Perceived Importance of Student Race		Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies		Support for Redistributive Educational Policies	
	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>

Student Study 4

Biased Growth Mindset Survey	2.98 (.94)		3.09 (1.03)						5.60 (1.06)			
Biased Fixed Mindset Survey	2.88 (1.08)		3.09 (1.12)						5.74 (1.01)			
Effect of Condition		.55		0						.94		

Condition	Fixed Mindset		System Legitimizing Beliefs		Perceived Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes		Perceived Importance of Student Race		Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies		Support for Redistributive Educational Policies	
	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>

Student Study 6

No Racial Disparity Conditions

Growth Mindset

Mission Statement	2.37 (.88)		3.06 (.98)		13.42 (8.15)		3.16 (1.25)		6.14 (.81)			
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Fixed Mindset

Mission Statement	2.43 (.91)		2.91 (1.04)		13.28 (10.56)		3.08 (1.25)		6.09 (.89)			
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Racial Disparity Conditions

Growth Mindset

Mission Statement	2.42 (.88)		2.99 (.98)		13.65 (10.41)		3.15 (1.20)		6.12 (.88)			
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Fixed Mindset

Mission Statement	2.40 (.88)		2.95 (1.03)		14.52 (13.84)		3.03 (1.19)		6.14 (.82)			
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Main Effect of Mindset

Manipulation		.05		1.98		.23		1.36		.11		
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Condition	Fixed Mindset		System Legitimizing Beliefs		Perceived Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes		Perceived Importance of Student Race		Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies		Support for Redistributive Educational Policies	
	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>

Student Study 7

Biased Growth Mindset Survey	2.91 (.82)		2.87 (.97)						5.78 (1.04)			
Biased Fixed Mindset Survey	2.66 (1.02)		2.81 (.98)						6.12 (.81)			
Non-Biased Survey Control	2.89 (.94)		2.73 (1.03)						5.95 (.88)			
Effect of Condition		1.40		.28						2.06		

Condition	Fixed Mindset		System Legitimizing Beliefs		Perceived Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes		Perceived Importance of Student Race		Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies		Support for Redistributive Educational Policies	
	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>
<i>Mturk Study 1</i>												
Biased Growth Mindset Survey	8.8 (6.58)				12.9 (10.8)		3.61 (1.27)		5.55 (1.19)		4.60 (.91)	
Biased Fixed Mindset Survey	8.4 (5.76)				13.1 (9.90)		3.23 (1.40)		5.95 (1.41)		4.32 (1.34)	
Growth Mindset Mission Statement	8.8 (5.31)				13.8 (9.03)		3.68 (.98)		5.55 (1.11)		4.02 (1.16)	
Fixed Mindset Mission Statement	8.4 (5.94)				14.9 (8.99)		3.40 (1.58)		5.88 (1.02)		4.11 (1.40)	
Control Condition	7.9 (4.53)				13.9 (7.84)		3.79 (1.29)		5.96 (.87)		4.50 (1.03)	
Effect of Condition		.10				.13		.58		.67		.85

Condition	Fixed Mindset		System Legitimizing Beliefs		Perceived Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes		Perceived Importance of Student Race		Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies		Support for Redistributive Educational Policies	
	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>
<i>Mturk Study 2</i>												
Biased Growth Mindset Survey	10.6 (6.68)				15.9 (8.96)		3.57 (1.16)		5.92 (.93)		4.50 (1.24)	
Biased Fixed Mindset Survey	9.1 (5.83)				10.5 (9.58)		4.11 (1.49)		5.70 (1.37)		3.81 (1.64)	
Control Condition	7.9 (5.36)				13.0 (6.98)		3.30 (1.56)		5.86 (.91)		4.30 (1.04)	
Effect of Condition		.94				1.91		1.71		.20		1.39
<i>Mturk Study 3</i>												
Biased Growth Mindset Survey	6.7 (4.78)				14.3 (8.89)		4.27 (.89)		5.50 (.91)		4.33 (1.10)	
Biased Fixed Mindset Survey	9.9 (5.05)				12.8 (8.63)		3.58 (1.34)		5.71 (1.19)		4.17 (1.23)	
Effect of Condition		9.44**				.40		8.54**		.94		.45

Condition	Fixed Mindset		System Legitimizing Beliefs		Perceived Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes		Perceived Importance of Student Race		Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies		Support for Redistributive Educational Policies	
	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>F</i>
<i>Mturk Study 4</i>												
Biased Growth Mindset Survey	7.9 (5.32)				14.7 (9.43)		3.86 (1.22)					4.28 (1.15)
Biased Fixed Mindset Survey	8.2 (5.05)				15.7 (9.46)		3.81 (1.29)					4.26 (1.13)
Control Condition	6.7 (4.28)				15.1 (9.29)		3.79 (1.30)					4.36 (1.11)
Effect of Condition		13.53**				1.18		.45				1.08
<i>Mturk Study 5</i>												
Growth Mindset Article	2.86 (1.11)				16.8 (8.31)		3.83 (1.33)		6.02 (.87)			4.49 (.80)
Fixed Mindset Article	4.09 (1.26)				13.2 (9.01)		3.65 (1.41)		5.86 (1.06)			4.53 (1.09)
Control Condition	3.47 (.97)				16.3 (9.31)		3.71 (1.33)		5.37 (1.16)			4.48 (1.05)
Effect of Condition		14.41**				2.26		.22		5.36**		.04

*Table 4.1. Correlations between measures of System Legitimization across Teacher and Student Studies. Note: Blank cells indicate that the study did not include both measures. *p<.05, **p<.01, ***p<.001, T = Teacher Study, S = Student Study*

Variables	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7	T8	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7
<i>System Legitimizing Beliefs</i>															
Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes	-.16***													-.04	
Downplaying the Importance of Student Race	.62***													.60***	
Race-Conscious Policy Support											-.39***	-.47***	-.49***	-.46***	-.45***
<i>Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes</i>															
Downplaying the Importance of Student Race	-.17**	-.15*	-.28***	-.07	.36***	-.02		-.20***						-.09**	
Race-Conscious Policy Support														.05	
<i>Downplaying the Importance of Student Race</i>															
Race-Conscious Policy Support														-.38***	

Table 4.2. Correlations between measures of System Legitimization across Mturk Studies. *Note:* Blank cells indicate that the study did not include both measures. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, M = Mturk Study

Variables	Study				
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5
<i>Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes</i>					
Downplaying the Importance of Student Race	.09	.17	.23*	.28***	.20*
Race-Conscious Policy Support	-.02	.21	.04		-.04
Redistributive Policy Support	.25*	.30*	.24*	.30***	.19*
<i>Downplaying the Importance of Student Race</i>					
Race-Conscious Policy Support	-.35**	-.29*	-.16		-.28***
Redistributive Policy Support	-.10	-.21	-.02	-.04	-.11
<i>Race-Conscious Policy Support</i>					
Redistributive Policy Support	.59***	.68***	.52***		.53***

Table 5. Results of Fixed Effects Models

Correlation between Fixed Mindset and...	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	95% CI		<i>z</i>	<i>k</i>
			LL	UL		
System Legitimizing Beliefs	.22	<.001	.18	.25	11.87	8
Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes	-.16	<.001	-.19	-.12	9.66	13
Downplaying the Importance of Student Race	.20	<.001	.17	.23	13.42	14
Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies	-.20	<.001	-.24	-.16	9.77	9
Support for Redistributive Educational Policies	-.21	<.001	-.25	-.16	8.66	5

Figure 1. Forest Plot of the Random Effects Model of the Relations between Fixed Mindset and Endorsement of System Legitimizing Beliefs

Figure 2. Forest Plot of the Random Effects Model of the Relations between Fixed Mindset and Perceptions of Institutional Responsibility for Student Outcomes

Figure 3. Forest Plot of the Random Effects Model of the Relations between Fixed Mindset and Perceived Importance of Student Race

Figure 4. Forest Plot of the Random Effects Model of the Relations between Fixed Mindset and Support for Race-Conscious Educational Policies

Figure 5. Forest Plot of the Random Effects Model of the Relations between Fixed Mindset and Support for Redistributive Educational Policies

